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HOUSING POLICIES IN NICARAGUA AFTER 1979

An Appraisal of the Sandinista's Housing Policies

The housing problem in Third World countries is alarming, and the number of people who are homeless or live in makeshift settlements under miserable conditions was estimated to exceed one billion in 1987, the "International Year of Shelter". A number of strategies, including sites-and services, slum upgrading, core housing and similar alternatives, have been tested almost everywhere, but they have been unable to stop the housing deficit from worsening. Most experts agree that housing is only a secondary problem, and can hardly be solved without a wider and simultaneous redistribution policy on the national if not the international level. Therefore, when the Nicaraguan Revolution succeeded in July 1979 and the Sandinistas started to convert the capitalist economy of the previous Somoza regime into a mixed economy with a strong social bias, it was felt that one of the greatest obstacles to solving the housing problem appeared to be out of the way. Everyone was curious to find out which housing policy the Nicaraguans would choose, and what could be achieved when there was mutual support between the government and the popular classes can be assumed. If the Nicaraguan model were successful, this might give hope to the millions of homeless in many parts of this world and encourage other governments to adopt at least some elements of its policy.

THE SITUATION AT THE BEGINNING OF THE REVOLUTION AND THE FIRST STEPS THEREAFTER

In Nicaragua, housing has been a problem for a long time. The 1971 census recorded that 61 per cent of dwellings had only dirt floors, 46 per cent were without sanitary facilities, 36 per cent had no access to water, and 59 per cent lacked electricity. In 1972 a severe earthquake hit the capital, Managua, killing 10,000 people and destroyed 50,000 houses. In the following years little was invested in housing, and none of it benefitted the poor. Further losses were suffered during the battles which preceded the liberation and by a flood in 1982. More

recently, the war with the contras (US-financed counterrevolutionaries) caused a death toll of not less than 43,000 and displaced more than 150,000 people. (Curutchet, 1987:135, Vance 1987a:170/71). In September 1988 the country was severely hit by a hurricane which erased whole settlements at the atlantic coast. Alone in Managua, several hundred kilometers from the coast, more than 1000 were completely destroyed, and another 30,000 heavily damaged.

Nicaragua is a small country with a surface area of 129,541 square kilometers and a population of 3.5 million in 1987 (MINVAH 1987:*). When the Sandinista government gained power it inherited a housing deficit of 250,000 units, which meant that two thirds of the population were in need of decent housing¹. It was calculated that this deficit would increase at a rate of 40,000 units per year, of which 25,000 could be attributed to decay of existing stock, plus an additional demand of 15,000 would arise from the natural population growth (MINVAH 1984a).

It would have been unrealistic to expect an instant solution from the new government. Apart from the fact that housing was only one among many pressing needs, the Sandinistas needed time, peace, and expertise to develop housing policies for their future society. Hence the most urgent difficulties had to be solved on an ad hoc basis, and some early decisions would need to be revised at a later stage. Many observers and "revolutionary tourists" were disappointed when they discovered problems of scarcity, incompetence, bureaucracy, and the like - limitations which have to be struggled against in any society, because these problems may have rather psychological and sociological reasons than political ones.

IS HOUSING A PRIORITY IN DEVELOPMENT?

Since by definition the financial investment capacity of developing countries is very limited, any state resources which may be spent on housing will be scrutinized on two levels at least: the benefits to the housing sector versus the benefits to other sectors; then once a decision is made in favour of housing, competition will ensue between different regions and between urban and rural areas.

Sectoral Priorities

Given the backlog in fixed industrial investment in all developing countries and the heavy burden of foreign debt, investment in the "productive" sector is normally granted priority over housing - which tends to be considered a mere consumption item or a social service at best. Usually under the threat of political uprisings will most governments be inclined to allocate more resources to the housing and consumption sector in order to maintain the stability of the political system.

In Nicaragua, which inherited an extremely high foreign debt from the prerevolutionary government, the prime development objective was the strengthening of the economic capacity of the nation, the means to achieve a positive balance of payments. This meant that

"productive investment" was perceived as the most important requirement to reach self-sufficiency in food production and to expand exports by means of improved cultivation of cash crops (particularly coffee, sugar, and cotton). Social expenditure in the field of education and health were given second priority over housing, since it was thought that they would have a greater, and direct effect on stimulating the economy, and because they would reach a greater number of people with the same, or more limited, resources: it has been argued, for example, that the literacy campaign, which benefitted almost 2 million Nicaraguans, was less costly than providing 2,000 families with a house (Arguello, 1985). However, even the ambitious social programs in health and education could not advance as programmed and had to be curbed, together with most housing programs once the imposed war absorbed an ever increasing share of the economy - eventually amounting to 60 per cent of all government expenditures. Due to this critical situation, the share of the budget earmarked for housing, which had reached almost 3 per cent of the GNP in 1982-1983, was cut back to about 1 per cent in 1986², or the fourth or fifth priority in order (Reyes 88). More recently, the Nicaraguan state taking sole responsibility to provide direct financing for housing has been questioned altogether. Instead, foreign aid has been explicitly declared a key source of funding for shelter projects (MINVAH, 1987:5).

However, in Nicaragua housing is not always considered a social expenditure or a consumption item. The Ministry of Agriculture, for example, emphasizes that adequate accommodation counts as a productive factor in agriculture (MINVAH, 1981:42), and it provides houses as an integral part of many of its own development schemes. In this sense, also the now dissolved Ministerio de la Vivienda y Asientamientos Humanos, or MINVAH (Ministry of Housing and Human Settlements) gave priority to those housing schemes which were linked to forestry, fishery, mining, and similar projects (Tapia, 1984:98).

Regional Priorities

The economic model pursued under the prerevolutionary Somoza regime had caused extreme regional imbalances in the pattern of fixed capital investment, provision of services, and the distribution of wealth. The urbanization process in the cities proceeded in an absolutely uncontrolled manner following the requirements of transnational capitalism, and turned the capital, Managua, into a typical "primate city" (Linsky 1969/72): although only 22 per cent of the nation's population lived in the city, 93 per cent of all sewerage installations, 85 per cent of all construction investment, and 80 per cent of all other investments were concentrated in Managua (Tapia 1984:91, Curutchet 1987:95). The strategy of the Sandinistas was intended to counterbalance this inherited pattern and to decentralize productive investment and political responsibilities step by step. For example, the share of all investments made in the Managua region was reduced to 66 per cent in 1981, and to 42 per cent in 1983 (Curutchet, 1987:95). The long term spatial distribution of the population was planned in accordance with the economic development potential of the regions. Assuming an overall population of 5

million in the year 2000, a hierarchical but balanced system of towns and smaller population centers was planned, with an even distribution of services throughout the country. In detail this plan, the Sistema Urbana Nacional (SUN) envisaged the following:

1. Managua would remain the capital and the most important administrative center, where the key services would be concentrated, i.e., the seat of government, national broadcasting, specialized hospitals, etc.
2. Nine centros regionales (regional centers) would contain a population of 20,000 to 100,000 each, and serve surrounding areas of an additional 50,000 to 500,000 inhabitants.
3. There would be 19 centros secundarios (secondary centres) with a population of 10,000 to 20,000 each, each with a surrounding area of 25,000 inhabitants
4. Fifty-five new or existing settlements with a population of 2,000 to 10,000 inhabitants would become centros de servicio (service centres) and provide centralized services for an additional 5,000 to 25,000 persons living in dispersed villages.

The plan assumes 70 per cent of the nation's population living in towns of more than 1,000 inhabitants, and 30 per cent rural population. If rural population currently constitutes 43 per cent of the total population (Third World Guide, 1989/90:422), we can see that further urbanization of the population is intended and that Managua will be permitted to grow much faster (140 per cent) than the nation as a whole (66 per cent). It may be disputable whether such a development is desirable and unavoidable, but the recent influx of refugees from rural areas into the cities (as a consequence of the war) may justify such a pessimistic prognosis. However, little thought seems to have been spent on how the negative social, ecological, and macroeconomic effects of such a fast urbanization can be avoided.

It is certainly true that the internal logic of the war has forced the government to devote a higher proportion of its spending than planned for the two most backward "special development zones" in the eastern parts of the country, which coincide with the areas affected most directly by war damages. So far some 250,000 peasants have lost their homes and productive base and need to be rehoused. In 1986 the share of government-provided housing for the rural population reached 60 per cent (MINVAH, 87:8). New settlements have been built near the frontier, offering better protection than isolated hamlets, and a minimal infrastructure (like roads) has been constructed. In spite of additional investments pumped into the area for strategic installations and other military reasons, decentralization policies have been hindered by the war on the whole.

Figure 1: Proposed Distribution of the Population in the Year 2000

I. THE INSTITUTIONAL INSTRUMENTS

The State Apparatus

One of the first undertakings of the revolutionary government in 1979 had been the creation of the MINVAH, Ministerio de la Vivienda y Asentamientos Humanos (Ministry of Housing and Human Settlements), a fusion of the previous Viceministerio de Planificación Urbana (Town Planning Vice Ministry), the Oficina de Inquilinato (Rent Office), and the Banco de la Vivienda de Nicaragua (Housing Bank). As the name suggests, the ministry had two main departments, with distinct responsibilities:

- * The Dirección de Desarrollo Urbano (Physical Planning Office) is in charge of town and regional planning, including the preparation of master and development plans (but not implementation of own investments).

- * The Dirección General de Vivienda (Housing Department) is responsible for planning, programming, supervising, and implementing all investments made by the ministry. In practical terms its functions included the building and management of state housing projects, the redistribution of land, and the coordination of infrastructure and most services. (However, the provision of technical services belongs to the activities of specialized enterprises, such as: the Instituto Nicaraguense de Acueductos y Alcantarillas which is responsible for supply of drinking water, and sewers, the Instituto Nicaraguense de Energia which is responsible for electricity, street lights, or the former Juntas Municipales - now alcaldias - which are responsible for garbage collection, road surfacing, etc.).

Although the MINVAH had a great variety of responsibilities, and employed more staff than most other ministries, it ultimately depended on the Planning Ministry, which decides on the allocation of all monetary resources in the first place. Finance for individual housing projects is provided by the BIN, or Banco Inmobiliario de Nicaragua, S.A. (National Mortgage Bank), and from outside agencies (MINVAH, 1987:6). On the other hand, MINVAH had dependent subsidiaries on its own, such as the COVIN, or Empresa de Construcción de Viviendas Nacional (State Building Companies). Other state bodies, like the municipalities or the MIDINRA, or Ministerio del Desarrollo Agropecuario y de la Reforma Agraria (Ministry of Agriculture) may have their own planning boards, develop land, or build houses themselves, but they had to obtain the approval of the MINVAH before they could execute their schemes.

Over the years the MINVAH had grown into a "superministry" while at the same time the budget available for housing production and other activities in the responsibility of the ministry had declined because of the war economy. Therefore in 1988 the decision was taken to dissolve the MINVAH, and to distribute its former responsibilities among a greater number of independent institutions again: most tasks (like all aspect of urban and regional planning) have been passed on the regional governments, emphasizing the idea of decentralization and greater participation. Managua as a special case has maintained an independent office of urban development, infrastructure, and housing. MINVAH's former legislative responsibilities have been taken over by the "Nicaraguan Institute for territorial Structure" (INITER) at the central level. The construction of houses and infrastructure will be handled independently by the state construction enterprise COVIN.

Popular Participation

Without the support of large sectors of the population the Sandinista revolution could never have succeeded in overthrowing the Somoza regime. After the victory the reconstruction had to rely on intense cooperation of the local population, since a functioning state apparatus was yet to be built. Therefore, popular participation was seen as an integral ingredient of national

housing policy:

"Through their mass organizations the population actively participated in the elaboration and application both of the provisions laid down in the plan, and in other political decisions with a direct impact of the peoples future" (MINVAH, 1983:24; translation by the author).

Formal instruments of popular participation have been introduced in two spheres: political control and execution of policy. In many instances the organized community has demonstrated successful examples of fertile negotiations with the authorities in cases where the bureaucracy failed to adequately satisfy their demands. One of the first instances of such a negotiation process in the field of housing is the case of the Barrio San Judas in Managua (c.f. Vance, 1987a and 1987b).

The main instruments of participation are the mass organizations, and among these in particular the former CDS, or Comité de Defensa Sandinista (Sandinista Neighborhood Committees), the MPS, or Milicias Populares Sandinistas (Militia), the AMLAE, or Asociación de la Mujer Nicaraguense Luisa Amanda Espinosa (women's organization), the (Juventud Sandinista 19 de Julio (Sandinista Youth Clubs), and the labor unions. At least initially most of these mass organizations constituted a formal part of the Sandinista Party System FSLN (Frente Sandinista de Liberación Nacional), but since these organizations are locally based and primarily concerned with practical day-to-day problems and their solutions, many citizens join these groups without being a member of the party or even when they belong to a different political party³. Reflecting this variety of different political standpoints, and realizing the necessity of grass roots activities for the reconstruction of the country after the war, the formal link with party was first given up for the neighbourhood committees in 1988 after public and frank discussions, and the women's organization followed soon after. The latter changed its name into Movimiento Luisa Amanda Espinoza (MOLAE), whereas the reorganized neighbourhood committees are now called "Community Development Committees" and primarily concerned with issues of local self-government and administration (Light, 1988. A detailed analysis of mass organizations in Nicaragua can be found in Ruchwarger, 1987).

The neighborhood committees play a key role in popular participation. In many ways they are organized in a similar fashion as the Comités de Defensa de la Revolución, or CDRs, in Cuba, except that in Nicaragua they already existed before the revolution, when they worked underground. The CDSs operate on several levels, starting from the block and street level, at the neighborhood level, where they were named Comité de Barrio Sandinista (CBS), at the municipal (zona), the regional, and at the national level. At the local base level special interest committees exist everywhere and take care of specific tasks, such as vaccination campaigns and preventive medicine (i.e., sanitation awareness), cooperation with solidarity

groups abroad, cultivation of communal gardens to grow basic crops, improvement of infrastructure, reforestation etc. (Mathéy, 1984:117). Sometimes the local CDS organizes or coordinates voluntary house building and infrastructure improvement activities (Curutchet, 1987:69, Darke, 1987:110). These voluntary work campaigns have become known under the name rojo y negro (red and black) - which are the colours of the Sandinista movement.

At the central level representatives of the CDSs were installed in all ministries, where they became members of the CPCs (Program Coordination Commissions). However, because there was no direct linkage between the local CDS representation and the decentralized executing branches of the authorities, grass roots control was often thwarted, i.e., in the allocation of vacant sites, or the repair of deficient services (Mathéy 1984:113). With the reorganization of the neighborhood committees at the base level in 1988, their central representation was under revision as well at the time of writing.

An illustrative and also very concrete example of popular participation in the field of housing is the prescribed mechanism for sites and building materials within a housing project being is the responsibility of a local committee. These committees, the outcome of a cooperation agreement between the MINVAH and the CDS in September 1983 (Ruchwarger, 1987:170), are named CRALOMBA, or Comité Regional de Asignación de Lotes y Módulos Básicos, consists of one representative from the ministry (MINVAH until 1988), one representative of the regional government, of the party (FSLN), the CST, or Central Sandinista de Trabajadores (trade union), and the neighbourhood committee CDS (MINVAH, 1984:13). When any **new houses** have to be allocated the selection of applicants is normally left to the local CDS, which has the most intimate knowledge about the applicant's objective housing need and merit in terms of contributing to the solution of neighborhood problems. Any disputes or subsequent tenancy conflicts are transferred to one of the regional committees, Comités Regionales de Asuntos Habitacionales (CRAHs), which were established in February 1984, and are composed of one MINVAH official and two representatives of the mass organizations (MINVAH 1984a:18). In both cases the ultimate power lies with the delegates of the mass organizations, since decisions are made by simple majority vote.

NON-PHYSICAL IMPROVEMENTS OF THE HOUSING SYSTEM

Land Policy

In a mixed economy the questions of land ownership and privately rented housing tend to be highly conflictive, since the vested interests of private capital rarely harmonize with the requirements of a socially oriented housing policy. Before the revolution, Nicaragua witnessed an excessive practice of land speculation particularly by the Somoza family, so there was a general consensus that their land should be expropriated once the Sandinistas had

taken power. However no attempt was made to nationalize all land, since many smaller landowners had been supporters of the Sandinistas, and real estate had been one of the few means of investment for the middle classes in an environment of steep inflation, without necessarily aiming at speculative gains. The main interest of the revolutionary government was to rectify the injustice which land speculation had brought about in the past and to inhibit any further speculation in the future.

Only a few weeks after the Sandinistas had taken power, they prohibited the sale of deeds for unserviced land (*Ley de Repartos Ilegales*, 1979) and thereby stopped the previous practice of speculative land subdivisions where the poor had to pay exorbitant sums for small plots in neighborhoods which did not deserve any other name than that of a slum: no water, no sewage, no paved streets, etc. By a subsequent law, the land of the existing 420 shanty towns (with 84,000 lots) was expropriated, and the ownership transferred to MINVAH. Any rents or leases which the occupants of the land continued to pay, would then be re-invested by the MINVAH in urgently needed services and infrastructure⁴, before the land title would eventually be transferred to the occupants. Of the expropriated sites 13,000 were immediately passed on to the occupants, since their accumulated payments over 20 or more years were estimated equal or superior to the value of the land (*Ley de Titulación de Lotes*, 1982).

The private ownership rights over land not used to satisfy the housing needs of its owner were further restricted in 1981 (*Ley de Expropiación*, 1981) and 1983 (*Ley de Bonos de Expropiación*, 1983): any vacant urban land which has been zoned for residential use, could be expropriated under the condition that it was needed for a public interest development - including housing. The previous owners were entitled to a compensation. However, since 1983 such a compensation has been made in the form of certificates which can only be exchanged for money after 20 years. These provisions were intended to inhibit the speculation of urban land, and not to nationalize land in general: in the countryside, for example, some 30 per cent of the 377 hectares of land expropriated under this law had been reprivatized by 1984 (MINVAH 1984b).

As long as MINVAH existed the transfer of ownership of land was regulated in order to keep speculation under control, and all property changes required clearance by the ministry (MINVAH up to 1988). But at present there is no restriction on the transfer of building sites between individuals.

To summarize the land policy in Nicaragua, private ownership of land was maintained, and even sanctioned if the land was to be used by the owner himself. In fact, the number of landowners increased significantly as a result of the rural and urban land reform laws. Except for the cases of expropriations, there was no monetary value set on the land, and small farmers or residents of Urbanisaciones Progresivas (see below) do not have to pay for land for

the time being. However, a revision of this practice has been on the agenda for a number of years, but was deferred due to the chaotic economic situation caused by the war, with inflation amounting to several hundred percent a year. The idea is to let people pay for the urbanization cost of vacant land, but not to charge a commercial price ruled by supply and demand.

Tenure Groups and housing rights

Different forms of housing tenure are sometimes promoted or attacked on ideological grounds. For example, owner occupation is understood to reinforce capitalist relations, and private renting is perceived as an instrument for exploitation because a landlord letting rooms or part of a house derives income by taking advantage of his capital, and not from a 'productive' activity.

In fact, in prerevolutionary Nicaragua more than 30 per cent of the population was paying rent (Ruchwarger, 1987:171), and the majority of renters belonged to the poor which, as in most other countries, had little opportunities of defending themselves against unscrupulous landlords. So it came as a great relief to the poor when early in 1980, half a year after the victory of the revolution, all rents were reduced to 40 to 50 per cent of their previous value (Ley de inquilinato, 1980). It was claimed that this measure benefitted some 72,000 families. Similar to the provisions made in relation to the illegal subdivisions, it was further foreseen that in cases where the landlord does not provide for the appropriate maintenance and repairs of the property, the state can intervene on behalf of the tenant and carry out the necessary repairs directly with the rent paid by the tenant. Although this legislation for the protection of tenants and leaseholders is indeed very favorable in theory, it is not always very practical. Cases have been reported, for example (Sanchez, 1984) where the new reduced rent was lower than the mandatory rates and taxes, which obviously produces a financial problem to a landlord willing to fulfil his responsibilities in regards to repairs and maintenance of the property.

In 1982 an even more radical bill was proposed by the government to outlaw private rental housing altogether - again on the principle that a tenant would have paid off the cost of a house after 20 years of rent payments. However, this bill was extensively discussed by the public at all levels, and substantially modified and tempered before its eventual approval in 1983:

"Before the government presented the law to the Council of State, CDSs in all major cities organized neighborhood assemblies to promote mass discussion and debate on its provisions. The country's newspapers published the complete text of the law. The Council of State received the final proposal only after public input substantially altered the law. Some CDS members argued that although the law would weaken the power of the big landlords, it could also

indiscriminately affect poor and working-class families who rent a wing of their homes or own some extra small property to augment their modest income. Others felt that inheritance restrictions might hurt poor families. The government took these criticisms into account and added special clauses and exceptions to avoid adverse affects among the popular classes." (Robinson, 1984:313).

The same provisions which had been proposed for private renters also apply to the housing stock owned or managed by the government: the ownership of these dwellings is automatically transferred to the tenants after a maximum period of 20 years (the exact length of the renting period depends on the income of the tenant, since the rent paid is calculated not to exceed 15 per cent of family income - and is revalued periodically in line with inflation)(MINVAH, 1987:5). On the other hand severe sanctions are foreseen in the cases of rent arrears and may include the forcible removal of the family from the dwelling (Sanchez, 1984).

The principle of private home ownership was never challenged in Nicaragua. On the contrary; owners can obtain credits for home construction⁵, and a good number of dwellings from the state housing stock have been sold to their occupants over the last years.

HOUSING PRODUCTION

Housing Sectors and Output

We tend to measure the success of a nations housing policy by the number of units completed within a certain time span. However, for the majority of the population other non-material elements of a housing policy, such as the introduction of rent control or land reforms can have a much more significant impact than the construction of a limited number of houses which are then allocated to a lucky few. We should keep this in mind when we look at the figures of new housing provided by the Nicaraguan state. These housing construction figures certainly read very favorably when they are compared with housing production performance under the Somoza regime (1,617 houses between 1966 and 1970 according to Vigil 1983:2), but they are nevertheless unable to catch up with the need generated by the natural population growth alone, not to speak of a chance to alleviate the deficiencies of the housing stock inherited by the revolution.

In terms of physical housing production, Nicaraguan housing policy operates four distinct programs for mass housing projects, building materials banks, the progressive development programme, and settlement upgrading.

Housing Complexes

This mass housing program supplied finished houses and appartments (complejos habitacionales) of a relatively high standard. It appeared to be the favoured approach of the Ministry of Housing in the first years after 1979. The houses are built by "direct labor" through the state construction company COVIN. Each development comprised 150 or more units, and was frequently linked to a new production enterprise (i.e., mining or agriculture). The rent is related to the building cost, which makes it too high for the average population. This may be the reason why in Managua, where 42 per cent of the produced units were located a high percentage of civil servants can be noticed among the beneficiaries⁶. The remainder was built in León, the second biggest city (23 per cent), and in rural areas (30 per cent) (MINVAH, 1984b: 30-31; MINVAH, 1987:9). In Total 9,536 dwellings have been completed under this scheme between 1980 and 1986, after which it was discontinued because of the restrictions of the war economy.

Self-Help Programs and Building Materials Banks

Already before the victory of the revolution several self-help housing projects of the 'core housing' type had been launched with World Bank funding in Nicaragua. After 1979 these projects were completed in line with initial plans, except for a change in the criteria applied in the selection of participants: for the last 700 units (spread over 13 project areas - MINVAH, 1984) the applicant's participation in communal activities was also taken into consideration, apart from financial acceptability. However, further sites-and-services projects, which continued to be popular in other Latin American countries, were rejected in Nicaragua on the grounds that they would reinforce individualism as opposed to collectivism (Vance, 1987a:172)

Formal Proyectos de Autoconstrucción (self-help projects) were replaced by the programme of the Bancos de Materiales (building materials bank), and initially targeted at those applicants who were in possession of a building site or who lived in a house in urgent need of repair (mejoramiento habitacional). These people could purchase loose building materials or complete kits for a standard house at very favourable, controlled prices. In 1983, prefabricated timber houses of 36 square meters were introduced as an alternative option. The so called módulos básicos made extensive use of indigenous building materials and could be assembled by the users within a few hours. Unfortunately, the production capacity for these units was drastically reduced when the sawmill of Ocota was destroyed by the "Contras" in 1984 (Curutchet, 1987:67). Meanwhile the demand for shelter increased significantly, particularly among those who became homeless through the war, and a more modest solution was introduced with a plan techo (roof-only version) to cope with the difficult situation. Altogether 12,269 módulos básicos and 5,655 roof-only-units were distributed between 1980

and 1986, and 95 per cent of these solutions benefitted the rural population (or 70 per cent of the módulos), with a preponderance to zones most affected by the war.⁷ In addition to this figure, another 3,419 units were provided directly by the MIDINRA or by other institutions (MINVAH, 1987:10 & Cuadro 4).

Progressive Urbanization

In the main cities of Nicaragua the housing problem was too big to be dealt with through the programs of the complejos habitacionales or the módulos básicos alone, at least in the short and intermediate term. Therefore, as a complementary measure, an ad-hoc response was introduced in 1982, which became the main instrument to rehouse the victims of the flood in Managua in the same year. Alternative sites in so-called urbanizaciones progresivas with basic infrastructure (communal water taps, electricity, public transport) were given to those people who had become homeless, and free transport was offered to move all reusable building materials from their previous shacks. In an attempt to gain control over the increasing squatter settlements since 1984, the "progressive urbanization programme" was extended and benefitted particularly those who had settled on geologically unsafe land (earthquake and flooding hazards) or on sites earmarked for uses other than residential.

At first sight the concept of the urbanizaciones progresivas appears similar to the sites-and-services projects known in other countries. However, there are several quite important differences. First, in Nicaragua the land is given to the settlers free of charge but with full security of tenure, which makes it possible to effectively reach that part of the population in the greatest housing need. Second, as the location of the urbanizaciones progresivas is always near to the main bus lines within the city and not far out in the periphery, the men and women can follow their habitual occupational pattern, often involving part-time and occasional jobs. And third, the principle of collective organization, political neighborhood representation, and communal work is fostered among the dwellers of these settlements - mainly by delegating important responsibilities to the CDS of the neighborhood. Up to 1984 63 per cent of the distributed sites were located in Managua (MINVAH, 1984b:34). In the following two years more emphasis was given to other cities, reducing the share of Managua to 55.7 per cent (MINVAH, 1987). Altogether some 28,800 plots had been allocated as part of the programme by 1986. This turns the scheme into the most significant contribution among the "physical elements" belonging to Nicaraguan housing policy.

Settlement Upgrading

Most urban houses, particularly in earthquake-ravaged Managua, are located in unplanned neighborhoods and lack some or all basic infrastructure and services. During the revolution

the support for the Sandinistas had been very strong from many of these places, and the population expected fast and visible improvements of their hitherto miserable conditions as the fruit of the revolution. Therefore the upgrading of these settlements was assigned a high priority within housing policy. However, since no official prospective land use planning existed for these areas, long term investments could only be made after the future of each particular settlement had been defined by the planning authorities. As land use plans proceeded, most of the 420 informal settlements were included in the Programa de Mejoramiento de Urbanizaciones, and approximately 50,000 families have benefitted in one way or another from the program in terms of receiving better services in the neighborhood - such as rain water drainage, a paved road, a day clinic etc. (MINVAH, 1987). Given actual economic constraints, upgrading has become the most important physical element of urban policies and implies that the government provide the necessary building materials, and the population contributes their own labour force (Reyes, 1988).

The impact of state housing programs

Adding up all the housing solutions offered as part of the various housing programmes (but excluding the sites distributed in the progressive developments, and neighborhood upgrading, where the impact is difficult to quantify) almost 28,000 dwellings were provided by MINVAH in 7 years: an average of 4,000 per year (or 1.14 units per 1,000 inhabitants). Assuming an occupancy rate of 6 persons per dwelling, we arrive at 6.85 houses completed for every 1,000 families, which means that every house would have to stand up for 146 years, or - taking a housing deficit of 377,000 units in 1981 - that the last person in need of a house today would have to wait 94 years to receive a government dwelling. Not included in this calculation is the additional demand of some estimated 15,000 units yearly arising from the natural population growth, or any extra houses to absorb internal migration flows. (The figures were derived from the tables supplied in MINVAH, 1984a).

We see that housing output by the state in Nicaragua does not appear particularly impressive, neither on its own, nor when compared with state housing programs in other countries. However, this relatively modest figure becomes meaningful when the composition of the target group is reviewed: In Nicaragua, by 1984 figures 17.8 per cent of the housing output reached the absolute poor earning less than 1 minimum wage, and another 78.1 per cent went to the next income bracket of 1 to 3 minimum salaries. This meant that only 4.1 per cent benefitted the middle and upper income groups. In typical low income housing programmes of other Latin American states, like the ones sponsored by the World Bank, the bottom 30 to 60 per cent of the population tend to be excluded because they are too poor to meet the financial obligations set by the programme (cf. Peattie, 1987:69-76).

The contribution of "Non-governmental agencies"

Since the beginning of the revolution a substantial number of foreign-based non-governmental agencies and solidarity groups supported various kind of development projects in Nicaragua - many of them also improving the housing situation locally. For some time this kind of cooperation was a potential field of conflict between the local community and central state institutions (Curutchet 1987:97): the organizations abroad often had established partnerships with specific neighborhoods in Nicaragua. Personal relations evolved, and helped to mobilize foreign funds to support a particular development project tailored to suit this specific community in Nicaragua. On the other hand, such a projects did not necessarily conform with the priorities set by the central planning authorities, who tied to guarantee a balanced and most rational use of limited resources. Furthermore the state tried to control and coordinate the help offered by foreign NGO through a central office in order to guarantee that all financial transactions connected with it were handled by the National Bank and exchanged at the official "commercial" exchange rate. As the spending capacity of the ministry of housing dried up as a consequence of the war economy, and inflation exploded, NGOs were given more freedom again to invest according to their own priorities. This is particularly true for the period from 1986 onwards. Since these organizations tend to work directly with the local communities, it is difficult to obtain a clear picture about the overall impact of their support, but my impression is that in the last years more houses have been built with NGO finance than from government funding.

The private and the informal sector housing

Although the Nicaraguan state acknowledges the right of each of its citizens to a decent home, this does not imply that the house has to be provided within the state or voluntary sector. After all, Nicaragua is a mixed economy, and mortgages are available to owner occupiers, but until recently they have had to compete with MINVAH for the very limited funds of the Banco Inmobiliario de Nicaragua S.A., or BIN⁸. A problem in the private sector entails the supply of building materials, which are extremely scarce and partially under state control (i.e., cement, lumber). There is a parallel market for these building materials, but the prices tend to be several times higher than at official outlets. Nonetheless, between 1983 and 1987 I noticed important private building activity in all neighborhoods, a phenomenon difficult to explain under such unfavorable economic circumstances, and calling for further research.

However, there are no indications that private housing is being built for sale or for lease on a commercial basis, which is - first of all - a positive indication for an effective legislation in favor of tenants and against property speculation. On the other hand the sharing of one dwelling by two or more families, or subletting to friends or distant members of the family without any financial interest, known as inquilenatos in many Latin American countries, is on the increase in Nicaragua.

The last resort for the urban homeless are the squatter settlements, and Nicaragua has experienced distinct periods when the homeless relied on these. One of these periods was immediately after the triumph of the revolution, in 1979 and 1980, when more than 25,000 people occupied some 4,400 vacant sites in the capital Managua, taking advantage of the disappearance of the oppressive police apparatus maintained by the Somoza regime (Curutchet, 1987:61). A second wave of squatting could be observed shortly before the elections in 1984 when it was very unlikely that the governing Sandinistas would risk a confrontation with the squatters. A third, and rather continuous movement in this direction has been since 1985 and can be attributed to the increasing number of refugees fleeing from the countryside where the war and the threat of massacres by the contras prevent a productive and peaceful life. Most recently, the damages caused by the 1988 hurricane forced many additional families into the cities and makeshift dwellings. However, in contrast to the neighboring nations squatters in Nicaragua do not risk forceful eviction by the police. Therefore there are no mass invasions or overnight building sites. Instead, an early process of grass roots organization and participation tends to take place, and the benefits of the established CDS structure enable negotiation with the authorities for an early provision of communal services and infrastructure.

THE CHOICE OF TECHNOLOGY

Options differ considerably regarding to the best choice of technology to satisfy the housing needs of a Third World revolutionary society. Some people think that the use of so-called appropriate technologies would help to serve a maximum number of people in a short time, and would save foreign exchange by relying on local building materials. Other experts argue that in the aftermath of a revolution the people expect better quality housing for everyone and that traditional building methods lack the necessary productivity to satisfy the increased demand.

In the case of Nicaragua the policy concerning the question of technology went through different phases. In the first two years after the revolution, there was a relatively open approach, and the construction of uniform concrete block houses (including those belonging to the World Bank's self-help programme) went on simultaneously with experiments in rammed-earth and bamboo construction, or similar appropriate technologies. For example, there were an experimental farm for bamboo at Rama, several adobe experiments in Managua, and a Center for Appropriate Technology (CITA) run by MIDINRA near Esteli. All these ventures were discontinued, albeit not for ideological reasons alone. The Rama farm was in the war zone, and stopped operating about 1983. MINVAH gave up its adobe experimentation site in Managua in 1982, which may have been a direct consequence of the fluctuation of staff in that period. The CITA/MIDINRA center was closed in 1985/1986 after internal management problems. (For an appraisal of CITA activities see Curutchet, 1987:81-87)

By 1983, the preference had shifted towards prefabrication and cement-based construction, and this tendency appears to be reinforced through the advice by state construction enterprise COVIN, and indirectly as well by cooperation with Cuban institutions. It was hoped, that the cost of the high quality complejos habitacionales could be lowered, and that the durability of the houses could be increased at the same time, as expressed in a publication of the MINVAH: "As a priority the housing demand created by rural and urban productive units will be satisfied by these housing development schemes (complejos habitacionales). In order to maximize the advantages of prefabrication and standardization in the production process these programmes are being carried with in heavy construction methods"(MINVAH, 1984b:8; translation by the author)

However, results from heavy construction and industrialized building methods in the housing sector were often disappointing, and the approach was also criticized on several occasions. It was reasoned, for example, that heavy construction would cause a too heavy drain on foreign exchange since 55 per cent of the cost of cement has to be spent on imported energy (Tapia, 1984:101) and that other high quality building materials and components (electric installations, metal fittings, ceramics) -- which are typical for the high quality construction of the housing complexes -- had to be imported and were difficult to obtain, which delayed the completion of the units unnecessarily (MINVAH, 1984b:45). Also the poor architectural design, and the incompatibility with Nicaragua's sociocultural context have been put forward in the discussion (MINVAH, 1981:84). Last but not least, even official publications imply that a higher productivity could not easily be achieved.⁹

Criticism of prefabrication and financial difficulties, as well as possibly also the explicit preference for less ambitious technologies expressed by international and nongovernmental agencies from abroad, helped in a consideration of a wider use of local materials and small scale-production. For example, several municipalities purchased low-cost machinery for the production of fibre cement roofing tiles, which would substitute industrially produced corrugated iron and asbestos cement sheets. More recently (1988), also the Technical University (UNI) started research into alternative building materials and methods.

CONCLUSION

At first sight, in looking at the absolute number of houses built by MINVAH since 1979, or measuring the problems of increased squatter settlements in Managua over the last four years, Nicaraguan housing policies do not suggest a great achievement. However, we must bear in mind that the Nicaraguans chose to put the main emphasis on non-physical improvements in housing provision and on social services in general, in order to benefit the largest number of people with the limited resources which were available. Within the wider field of social expenditure housing was assigned the third priority after health and education (Vance,

1987a:171).

Since 1981 the housing deficit has grown by 17,000 units annually (Ruchwarger, 1987:170). The declining output in government shelter projects and the overall worsening of housing stress in Nicaragua must be attributed in the first place to the escalating war in the country, which has been imposed on the country by the Reagan administration. This has drastically curbed the disposable budget for any housing construction. At the same time, the influx of refugees fleeing the ever present threat of contra devastations and genocide has frustrated the decentralization policy and produced a chaotic situation in the cities where too many people have sought new homes.

It may be true that not all problems encountered in the Nicaraguan housing system can be explained by the war. Due to the poor teaching facilities prevalent in the prerevolutionary period and the brain drain in response to the poor income opportunities, the level of professional and academic skills has been restricted - a condition affecting public authorities in particular when they seek to fill vacancies (because of the low wage levels they offer). There are additional problems of coordination and competition between different ministries and other state institutions, which need years to sort. Certainly these restrictions are endemic in most parts of the developing world, but they tend to be even more severe in periods following a political overthrow. Fortunately, the popular character of the Nicaraguan revolution set the foundations for a well-organized grass roots participation, and frequently the local community was able to offset many of the limitations coming from a more central economic or administrative level. This learning experience, which might not have been necessary under more peaceful conditions, will certainly help to build up a real grass roots democracy once the war has been overcome in Central America.

In spite of the many problems discussed, the housing policy implemented by the revolutionary government in Nicaragua favorably contrasts with conditions typical in other Latin American or Third World countries. It should be pointed out that **90 per cent of all state housing investment directly favors low income groups** (Tapia, 1984:101) -- a figure which would be difficult to encounter in any truly capitalist country, including the industrialized world.¹⁰ However, an even more remarkable and truly revolutionary achievement for the majority of the population is the **free access to land and basic services**, as provided within the urbanizaciones progresivas program in urban areas. In rural areas the Agrarian Reform represents a similar approach, since land titles are also distributed to small farmers free of charge, and housing is explicitly considered a productive (and not consumption) investment. By adopting these two principles other Third World countries would be able to solve at least part of their housing problem, but this would also imply sacrificing certain "freedoms" currently enjoyed by landed and finance capital and represent a step towards a mixed economy.

-----June 1989

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APPENDIX: HOUSING LEGISLATION 1979 - 1983

Ley de (intervención de) repartos ilegales (September 26,1979)

Prohibits the sale of plots in illegal subdivisions.

Ley de inquilinato (January 2,1980)

Reduction of all housing rents to 40-50 per cent of their previous value, except for high quality housing for which 5 per cent of its assessed value is the permitted maximum rent per year. In cases where the landlord fails to carry through the necessary repairs the government may intervene on behalf of the tenants and take over the management of these dwellings.

Ley de donaciones del casco urbano (January 4,1980, amended April 8, 1980, and May 5, 1980)

Municipalization of all unused sites in the center of Managua, for which a general development ban had been issued after the earthquake of 1972. Compensation is to be paid to the previous owners after deduction of all tax debts.

Ley de regulación de las cuotas de amortización de viviendas del sistema financiero nacional y del MINVAH (1980)

Reduction of mortgage payments to correspond with the average income situation of the population affected. All mortgage payments done within the past 20 years will be counted as downpayments towards the transfer of ownership to the occupants.

Ley creadora de la corporación nicaraguense de bienes raíces (CONIBIR) (April 4, 1980).

Creation of a subsidiary of MINVAH to handle the administration of the housing stock in MINVAH's care.

Ley sobre el uso del suelo en las áreas de desarrollo de los asentamientos humanos (August 30, 1980, amended May 12, 1983)

Transference of planning authority to MINVAH. Development plans (Planos de Desarrollo) and Zoning Plans (Planos Reguladores) are to be the binding planning documents.

Ley procesal de inquilinato (February 17, 1981, amended December 21, 1981, annuled July 6, 1983)

Procedural instructions related to the Ley de Inquilinato.

Ley organica de la corporación constructora de viviendas (August 31, 1981)

Creation of the state-owned direct labor and planning enterprise COVIN.

Reglamento de la ley organica de covin (December 11, 1981)

Procedural instructions related to the ley organica de la corporación constructora de viviendas.

Ley de expropiación de tierras urbanas baldias (December 14, 1981)

Provisions to enable the expropriation of any unused urban sites if needed for the public interest. The compensation to be paid in form of investment certificates at an annual interest rate of 2 per cent over a period of 20 years after which the value is due for cash payment (by 1985 some 377 hectares had been expropriated according to this law, and slightly more than 30 per cent of this land had been reprivatized again - see MINVAH, 1984).

Ley de expropiación de predios baldios en el casco urbano del centro de la ciudad de Managua (December 16, 1981)

Provisions for the expropriation of sites in central Managua.

Ley de titulación de lotes en repartos intervenidos (January 2, 1982, amended April 9, 1982 and October 7, 1982)

Provision of ownership titles to the owners or occupants of private sites under government administration.

Reglamento de la ley de titulación de lotes en repartos intervenidos (October 12, 1982)

Procedure instructions related to the "Ley de titulación"

Ley de bonos de expropiación de tierras urbanas baldias. (June 6, 1983)

Compensation for expropriated urban sites in the form of certificates.

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Notes:

1. In 1979 the population was 2,700,000, or 439,026 families. The housing stock consisted of 376,973 houses, which left 62,053 (14%) families without a home. Of the existing houses, 187,890 were substandard (only one room, or structurally dangerous), which adds up to a housing deficit of 249,943 (Curutchet, 1987:19)
2. The figure was extrapolated from figures published by MINVAH (1987). In 1981, 2376 dwellings produced representing 2.01 per cent of GNP; in 1982, 3476 (2.92 per cent); in 1983, 4121 (2.74 per cent); in 1984, 3631 (2.18 per cent); in 1985, 4567 (1.19 per cent); in 1986, 2171 (no percentage indicated).
3. Nicaragua is a multiparty state. Within parliament there are parties in coalition with the FSLN, and parties in the opposition - like the Liberals and the extreme left. The right wing parties, which cooperate with the US-financed contras, refused to take part in the 1984 elections.
4. This provision did not imply, that all the substandard neighborhoods could expect an instant improvement of their conditions: For example, while MINVAH had collected 20 million Córdobas from the residents in all substandard neighborhoods (MINVAH, 1984b:19), or 68,5 million córdobas derived from all 35,000 dwellings and 50,000 sites under its management in 1982; only 8,85 million córdobas were invested again in the improvement of 353 dwellings (Tapia, 1984:98).
5. Créditos Hipotecarios from the Banco Hipotecario for periods between 1 and 20 years, at an interest rate of 14-20%. If the credit is intended for purchase of a house the applicant must provide securities; for repairs there is no such requirement (MINVAH, 1987:6)
6. The observation was made by the author in the San Antonio project in 1987. This is not to say that civil servants enjoy a particularly high income - rather the opposite is the case and explains the phenomenon of the high fluctuation of staff in the state sector. Although I lack first hand information in this respect, I assume that civil servants have been offered these houses, which would be difficult to let at the market at the cost price, at a discount price to compensate for the low wages.
7. Region I (Las Segovias), Region IV (Matagalpa and Jinotega along the northern border to Honduras) and Special Development Zone III (Rio San Juan, on the border with Costa Rica) (Curutchet, 1987:135).
8. In the first years the share of the private sector loans was negligible. According to more recent sources (MINVAH, 1987:8) this share reached 55 per cent in 1986, although this figure was only given in relative terms. It might be that BIN funds channelled to MINVAH have declined to the war economy, such that similar or less funds for the private sector still represent the majority.

9. MINVAH (1984b) calculated a productivity rate of 3.3 (highest) for timber houses, 2.92 for conventional solid construction, and 2.3 (lowest) for the prefabricated small panel system known under the name SANDINO.
10. A comparison with socialist countries, such as Cuba or China, is more difficult, since there a key question might be how effectively income differentials were reduced in the first place.